

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers:

This is the first issue of year three of J.UCS: for an electronic journal that is going strong this must be quite a record! Note that this issue is still free, and maybe the next one will be too. However, Springer is working hard on getting their WWW accounting system working and then electronic journals will only be available for paying subscribers. We all hope that the number of persons using J.UCS is not going to dramatically reduced because of this!

I will report on the technicalities involved in accessing the journal once the subscription system is in place in one of the next issues, when the details are clarified.

For now, happy reading!

Yours cordially,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'H. Maurer', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

Hermann Maurer
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